

Horizon Europe

Data Management Plan

Version 1.0
20 February 2024

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication date	Changes
1.0	20.02.2024	▪ Initial version
		According to the guidelines of the MSCA, this Data Management Plan (DMP) is designed to evolve continuously as the project unfolds and significant developments arise. This initial version marks the beginning, with subsequent updates planned to provide more detailed information as the project advances. The DMP will undergo regular revisions as part of the project's periodic evaluations, ensuring it remains current and comprehensive. Updates will be completed well in advance of the final review.

Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2022-PF-01

(MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships 2022)

Topic: HORIZON-MSCA-2022-PF-01-01

Type of Action: HORIZON-TMA-MSCA-PF-EF. (HORIZON TMA MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships - European Fellowships)

Proposal number: 101103095

Proposal acronym: Trans Modernismo

Full title: Birth of the Marimacho: Modernismo's Trans* Cultural Productions in Latin America

Researcher: Dr. Carlos Gustavo Halaburda

Supervisor: Prof. Dr. Peter Schulze

Type of Model Grant Agreement: HORIZON Unit Grant

Department: Universität zu Köln. Department of Romance Studies. Germany

Starting Date: 1/09/2023

Duration (in months): 24

Scientific Area: SOC - Social Sciences and Humanities (SOC); Gender history; Cultural studies; cultural diversity; Literary theory and comparative literature; literary styles; Women and gender studies; Libraries and archives.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

1. Data Summary

My project *Birth of the Marimacho: Modernismo's Trans* Cultural Productions in Latin America* tells the history of a new gender expression in early-twentieth-century Latin American literature, medical science, and visual culture: the «marimacho». In the Hispanic tradition, *marimacho* is the umbrella notion that may refer to a sexist slur as much as a modern form of non-binary gender, a transmasculine identification, or a lesbian identity. This project examines the aesthetic construction of this hybrid, counter-cultural, and gender-dissident figure in an extensive cultural repertoire that includes novels, plays, silver films, leaflets, medical studies, prison and mental hospital records, poems, newspaper, and tabloid articles from the period 1880-1930. The purpose of data collection is to assemble a corpus of published and unpublished sources held in print and digital archives and special collections. These sources are copyright free and are available through open access in university digital repositories, national archives, and research institutes in Germany, France, Mexico, Spain, and Argentina. The main purpose of the data collection is to analyze its content through the methodologies of literary studies and gender theory in relation to the main research questions of the project outlined in the original proposal.

This project draws upon multiple theoretical schools and philosophical resources from gender and sexuality studies. Queer scholarship addresses not only the political self-representation of LGBTQ bodies. Queer studies also examine major problems in minority discourse: the medical stigmas around homosexuality and transness, the non-normative/non-reproductive uses of erotic pleasures, and the broad implications of 'gender dysphoria' for orthodox notions of citizenship. My analysis of the chosen corpus will demonstrate how queer men, lesbians and trans*men and women contested misogynist and sexual slurs by showing how gender and sexual orientation, far from being natural, are both constructed through performance and the adoption of diverse prosthetic artifacts, from hair and clothing to makeup and other cosmetic techniques.

My project examines published sources collected in national and university libraries with unrestricted access to literary and scientific magazine collections. But I also work with unpublished written documents such as medical histories, police documents, and court records of the historical period 1880-1930 in Argentina. My subjects of study are no longer alive. However, when I access National Archives, for example, in Argentina, I will comply with the rules of Personal Data and Personal Data Code relating to criminal convictions or offenses included in the Archivo General de la Nación in Argentina (AGN). The data will be used for research purposes only on the condition that there are appropriate safeguards for the rights and freedoms of the data subject. Honoring the AGN's role in preserving the documentation entrusted to it by law in Article 2 of Law 15930, I will be sensitive to personal data related to religious or philosophical beliefs, racial or ethnic origin, political opinion, sex life or sexual orientation. As for the ethics of representation, considering that I am a gay cisgender male investigator, I will continuously consult with trans* specialist, non-binary intellectuals, and lesbian scholars for an equitable outlook on my research conclusions.

The Trans Modernismo Project will produce mainly the following kinds of research data:

- Scientific publications in the Humanities (e.g., peer-reviewed publications: journals, book chapters, a monograph).
- Articles in mass channels of dissemination (newspaper editorials).

2. FAIR data

2. 1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The existing data collected for my project is discoverable in existing reference data bases. The data is identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism such as persistent and unique identifiers (for example, Digital Object Identifiers). For instance, the main digital archive that I use in my project is the Berlin Ibero-American Institute Digital Collections of Latin American Culture (<https://digital.iai.spk-berlin.de/viewer/index/>). All sources collected in this archive have persistent identifiers. Ej: Persistent identifier: 79291533X. Title: La machona. Creator: Margueritte, Victor. PURL: <http://resolver.iai.spk-berlin.de/IAI0000534700010000>.

The following archives and reference data bases are constitutive part of my project, but the list is not exhaustive. All data are stored in these institutions that have also digital repositories:

1. Ibero-Amerikanisches Institut - Stiftung Preußischer Kulturbesitz. <https://www.iai.spk-berlin.de/startseite.html>
2. Hemeroteca Nacional de España. Hemeroteca Digital. <https://www.bne.es/es/catalogos/hemeroteca-digital>
3. Ahira. Archivo Histórico de Revistas Argentinas. <https://ahira.com.ar>
4. The University and City Library of Cologne. <https://ub.uni-koeln.de/en/>
5. The NS-Documentation Center of the City of Cologne Library—Queer Collection. <https://museenkoeln.de/ns-dokumentationszentrum/default.aspx?s=315>
6. Manchester Central Library. Archive of the People’s History Museum of Manchester. Microfilm Collections on British Suffragism and World Feminist Networks. See details here: [http://gmlives.org.uk/results.html#imu\[rid=ecatalogue.262930\]](http://gmlives.org.uk/results.html#imu[rid=ecatalogue.262930])
7. Bibliothèque Nationale de France. <https://www.bnf.fr/fr>
8. Archivo Nacional de la República Argentina. <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/interior/archivo-general-de-la-nacion>

I will publish my results based on the existing data stored in these libraries. I will publish my work in peer review articles for Humanities/Literary Studies open access journals. I will provide keywords that optimize possibilities for my article to gain visibility, such as “gender,” “race,” and “sexuality studies.” In the digital repository Xenodo, besides uploading my scientific publications I will also publish a critical bibliography (my own collected list of works based on existing data) with the identifiers pertaining to each source collected and re-used by me, either primary sources or monographs with existing ISBNs (International Standard Book Number). Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artefacts. The data collected and presented in this critical bibliography is based on existing data and will look in the following manner:

Critical Bibliography

Primary Sources (Digital)

Berlin Ibero-American Institute Literary Periodicals

Timarni, A. *La machona* (Tango). Editor: Santorelli, Leonicio. La cancion del día. 1.1922/23=Nr. 6. Berlin: Ibero-Amerikanisches Institut - Preußischer Kulturbesitz, 1923. **Persistent identifier:** 814176445. PURL. <http://resolver.iai.spk-berlin.de/IAI0000544000000000>

Primary Sources (Print)

Bibliothèque National de France

Recueil factice d'art. de presse sur le Procès de "la Garçonne" de Victor Margueritte] [Texte imprimé] 10 pièces ; In-8 °.Identifiant de la notice: <ark:/12148/cb38678347c>. Notice n° : FRBNF38678347. PURL. <https://catalogue.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cb38678347c>

Secondary Sources

Velasco, Sherry Marie. *The Lieutenant Nun: Transgenderism, Lesbian Desire, and Catalina de Erauso*. University of Texas press, 2000. ISBN. 978-0-292-78745-2.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

Book chapters, critical bibliographies, editorials, peer review journals, and a final monograph in the field of Humanities and Literary Studies are the kind of results that I will produce. My work is based on existing data and will be made openly available as default.

As I mentioned, my work will be made accessible by deposition in the repository Xenodo. The first step will be to deposit a critical bibliography of the sources collected and used for interpretation. This document shall include existing data collected that are available in an unrestricted way in the institutions listed above. To access the data in these libraries and archives is necessary an internet connection, a browser, and/or a library research card for the corresponding institution. Researchers will be able to consult my sources freely and click on the DOIs to access the data already existing in these reference bases and re-use it. Xenodo is the best identified repository to make my data openly accessible. This repository is:

1. **Safe:** Research is stored safely for the future in CERN's Data Centre for as long as CERN exists.
2. **Trusted:** Built and operated by CERN and OpenAIRE to ensure that everyone can join in Open Science.
3. **Citeable:** Every upload is assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), to make them citable and trackable.
4. **No waiting time:** Uploads are made available online as soon as you hit publish, and your DOI is registered within seconds.
5. **Open or closed:** Share e.g. anonymized clinical trial data with only medical professionals via our restricted access mode.
6. **Versioning:** Easily update your dataset with our versioning feature.
7. **GitHub integration:** Easily preserve your GitHub repository in Zenodo.
8. **Usage statistics:** All uploads display standards compliant usage statistics.

2.3. Making data interoperable

My work (monographs, articles, book chapters, reference bibliography) will be deposited in Xenodo and will be openly accessible. As I mentioned, I work with existing data.

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

I work with existing data (literary and historical sources) available through open access in the corresponding libraries. I will not produce any re-usable data.

3. Allocation of resources

As of now, I have not identified journals with publication costs. Publications in the targeted journals are free of any cost. If there are costs, these will be covered by my Horizon Europe Grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions). I will be responsible for data management in my project. My results will be preserved mainly in the shape of scientific publications.

4. Data security

The existing data is stored in major libraries and collections. The data are safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation. As for my own scientific publications and other documents produced during my project, these will be published in Xenodo. The rules of Xenodo for longevity of the data are:

- **Versions:** Data files are versioned. Records are not versioned. The uploaded data is archived as a Submission Information Package. Derivatives of data files are generated, but original content is never modified. Records can be retracted from public view; however, the data files and record are preserved.
- **Replicas:** All data files are stored in CERN Data Centres, primarily Geneva, with replicas in Budapest. Data files are kept in multiple replicas in a distributed file system, which is backed up to tape on a nightly basis.
- **Retention period:** Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.
- **Functional preservation:** Zenodo makes no promises of usability and understandability of deposited objects over time.
- **File preservation:** Data files and metadata are backed up nightly and replicated into multiple copies in the online system.
- **Fixity and authenticity:** All data files are stored along with a MD5 checksum of the file content. Files are regularly checked against their checksums to assure that file content remains constant.
- **Succession plans:** In case of closure of the repository, best efforts will be made to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.
- <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

5. Ethical aspects

My work examines published sources collected in national and university libraries with unrestricted access to literary and magazine collections. My subjects of study are mainly fictional or no longer alive. As I stated in my in the Description of the Action (DoA), this project is committed to a transformative scholarly framework that validates the memory of stigmatized Latin American gender and sexual minorities. It seeks to recognize and give visibility to the epistemic, cultural, and institutional violence endured by the LGBTQ community. This project addresses the late nineteenth- and early twentieth-century legacies of homophobia, transphobia, and misogyny recorded in the literary and scientific

archives of the region. In my combination of literary criticism, historical work, archival research, and the critique of past sexual and medical taxonomies, I read against the grain of the original violence that represented LGBTQ peoples as abject subjects unworthy of full citizenship in the cultural production of the period 1880-1930. My research follows the values of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union regarding personal data protection and information and equality between genders. I follow the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols, paying attention to article 14, Protection from discrimination in respect of these rights and freedoms. The Human Rights Act makes it illegal to discriminate on a wide range of grounds including sex, race, color, language, religion, political or another opinion, national or social origin, association with a national minority, property, birth, or another status.